

A Non-parametric Analysis of Productivity Growth in ECOWAS Agricultural Sector (1980 – 2022)

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ABSTRACT

Agricultural productivity and competitiveness does not match its potential in ECOWAS due to widespread of low agricultural productivity, food insecurity and many other interrelated factors like difficulties accessing factors of production; the steady degradation of the soil and climate; irregular rainfall in the region and lack of control over water resources; increasing poverty and lack of control over stocks of foodstuffs; and political crises linked to wars and to the democratization process among member countries. This study employed the use of a panel data of 12 Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) member states on output and conventional agricultural inputs spanning through 1980 to 2022. Specifically, the study estimates the trends of different production factors influencing the value of agricultural production among ECOWAS member states and decomposes Total Factor Productivity (TFP) of the agricultural sector of ECOWAS member states into its major components using Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) Malmquist productivity indexes. The results show that agricultural TFP growth rate in ECOWAS has been declining due to technological regression and efficiency stagnation in the sub-region within the reference period, even as all the 12 studied member states experienced negative Total Factor Productivity (TFP) growth rate. This study therefore recommends increased investment in farm mechanization (tractorization) as well as increased investment in agricultural production inputs, technologies and practices to boost agricultural production and drive ECOWAS agricultural productivity growth.

1. INTRODUCTION

The role of agriculture has been identified to be quite significant in many developing economies of the world, especially economies in Africa and ECOWAS in particular, where a larger proportion of their population reside in the rural area, depending largely on agriculture for survival (Nchuchume and Adejuwon, 2012; Wiggins *et al.*, 2013). Agricultural

productivity growth in West Africa has been declining as the per-capita GDP has surpassed per-capita agricultural GDP in the sub-region despite all efforts deployed by the member states and may have been worsen due to many interrelated factors like political crises linked to wars and to the democratization process; the steady degradation of the soil and climate; difficulties accessing factors of production; increasing poverty and lack of control over stocks of foodstuffs; irregular rainfall in the region and lack of control over water resources. Agricultural output growth in ECOWAS therefore requires heavy investment in modern technology, research and managerial expertise considering its low agricultural productivity profile despite large expanse of agricultural land areas and agricultural population. (Ogbonna *et al.*, 2013; UNECA, 2012).

The agricultural sector in the ECOWAS region, like in many African economies, holds a vital position within society. It is widely regarded as the cornerstone and foundation of the economy, exerting a multifaceted impact on various aspects such as employment, income, and food security (ECOWAS Commission, 2010; Efobi and Osabuohien, 2011). The sector makes a substantial contribution, accounting for approximately 35% of the gross domestic product (GDP) of the ECOWAS sub-region, and it represents about 16.3% of the total value of goods and services exported. On average, over 60% of the working-age population in the ECOWAS region is engaged in agriculture, underscoring its significant potential for poverty alleviation and the assurance of food security (ECOWAS Commission, 2010; Efobi and Osabuohien, 2011).

This study broadly analyzed the total factor productivity of ECOWAS agriculture from 1980-2022. The study specifically estimated the trends of the different production factors influencing ECOWAS' value of agricultural production and decomposes its agricultural sector's Total Factor Productivity (TFP) into its major components. This was achieved by providing answers to the following research questions: What are the trends of various production factors influencing value of agricultural production among ECOWAS member states? To what extent has

the growth in agricultural output in ECOWAS member states being catered for by the growth in various physical inputs, and components of TFP?

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

There are the initial fifteen-member nations of the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) with different colonial indoctrinations, which share strong historical, geographical, cultural, and economic affiliations. However, these West African countries often cut across ethnic and cultural lines, dividing single ethnic groups between two or more countries. While these countries may have different resource endowments, they share various similarities such as low per capita income, poor infrastructure development, high levels of debts, corruption, and political instability. Another shared characteristic among ECOWAS members is a poor domestic savings culture. The sub-region has experienced fluctuations in commodity prices (particularly oil), currency depreciation, and imbalances in import-export trade (Anifowose, 2016).

ECOWAS is divided into two sub-regional blocs: The West African Economic and Monetary Union (UEMOA) and the West African Monetary Zone (WAMZ). The UEMOA which was established in 1994 consists of eight predominantly French-speaking countries within ECOWAS that share similar traditional practices and a currency union. These countries use a common currency, the CFA franc, which is pegged to the euro. On the other hand, the WAMZ, established in 2000, consists of six English-speaking countries in the sub-region. The WAMZ has been planning to adopt a common currency known as the eco, but its implementation has faced delays (ECOWAS Commission, 2010; Anifowose, 2016).

The agricultural sector plays a crucial role in the economies of the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) member countries. It remains a significant contributor to the regional GDP, foreign trade, employment opportunities, poverty reduction efforts, and food security. Despite facing challenging production environments and hostile trade practices from some developed nations that continue to subsidize their farmers, the agricultural sector in ECOWAS countries has demonstrated remarkable resilience (ECOWAS Commission, 2024). The sector has proven highly adaptable, with production increasing sufficiently to meet the growing demand. Export crops such as coffee, cotton, cocoa, and others have performed relatively impressively, recording significant successes over time (ECOWAS Commission, 2024).

It is widely believed that the agricultural sector of ECOWAS countries has the potential to perform even better under a regional development strategy tailored specifically for the sector. This strategic approach could further enhance the sector's contribution to the region's economic growth and development. The Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) adopted the ECOWAS Regional Agricultural Policy (ECOWAP) on January 19, 2005, as the guiding policy initiative for the agricultural sector in the region. ECOWAP serves as the appropriate reference for reviewing and developing regional agricultural policies (ECOWAS, 2016).

Concept of Productivity Growth

Productivity, as a major concept in economics, is defined as the output derived per unit of input utilized in the production process (Coelli and Rao, 2003). Productivity is a fundamental concept that measures the ratio of output to input in a production process. The Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO, 2021) defines productivity as the ratio of a volume measure of output to a volume measure of input use. This measurement can be applied to a single entity, such as a farm or commodity, or to a group of farms at various geographical scales. Inputs are the production factors that undergo transformation into outputs through the production process. This process entails the conversion of input factors into output products.

Productivity has an effect on the growth of organizations, economies, and sectors. Increased productivity results in enhanced performance (increased production) and higher profits (minimal factor costs, better selling prices, marketing capacities, etc. (Chebil *et al.*, (2015). Productivity growth is considered essential for the agricultural sector to align with the rising demands for food and raw materials arising from steady population growth. Consequently, productivity growth is generally defined in terms of the improvement and technical change with which inputs are transformed into outputs in the production process (Pfeiffer, 2004; Ajao, 2012; Ajetomobi, 2009).

Over the past few decades, productivity growth has garnered significant attention, as it is perceived to be the major determinant for developing the agricultural sector of all economies (developed, developing, and underdeveloped) at a rate that will enable them to meet their local demands for food and raw materials, thereby catering to their respective populations. Failure to achieve agricultural productivity growth may lead to setbacks in areas such as comparative advantage in export markets, foreign exchange balance, and internal terms of trade against

industry, consequently hindering industrial production capacity. Conversely, a country that maximally utilizes its given resources within its agricultural sector may enjoy a significant comparative advantage in export markets (Coelli and Rao, 2003). Mugeru and Ojede (2011) characterize productivity growth as a measure of output growth that cannot be attributed to changes in factor inputs. In essence, productivity is the ratio between outputs and inputs, and productivity indexes can be expressed as the ratio of an aggregate output index to an index for total factor use.

According to FAO (2021), in assessing growth, sustainability, and competitiveness in the agricultural sector, the proper identification and measurement of agricultural productivity growth are crucial, particularly when technical change in the sector is factor-biased rather than Hicks-neutral. Studies on productivity growth have employed either Partial Factor Productivity (PFP) measures, such as labor productivity (McErlean and Wu, 2003), or Total Factor Productivity (TFP) measures. TFP measures have been empirically analyzed using: a production function approach (Hayami and Ruttan, 1970; Wiebe *et al.*, 2000); an index number approach, usually the Tornqvist index (Mukherjee and Kuroda, 2003), or a Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) approach, such as the DEA-based Malmquist index (Coelli and Rao, 2003; Ludena *et al.*, 2005).

Empirical review on agricultural productivity

Baion *et al.*, (2023) in their study compared the performance of agricultural productivity in 44 Sub-Saharan African countries within the span of 59 years (1961- 2019). Data was extracted from the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations with Malmquist productivity index approach used in analyzing the data. The extent and nature of growth in Sub-Saharan countries were investigated using non-parametric frontier techniques using data envelopment analysis (DEA) in obtaining Malmquist productivity indices, and the study reported a decrease in the agricultural TFP in the region from 1961-2019.

Adeleke *et al.*, (2017) worked on productivity growth, technical progress, and Efficiency Change in ECOWAS Agriculture 1971-2009, using a full cumulative (FC) Extended Malmquist Approach. They employed the use of country-level panel data on agriculture in ECOWAS to investigate Total Factor Productivity growth in the region from 1971 to 2009. The TFP growth of ECOWAS agriculture was also measured using the Full Cumulative (FC) Extended Malmquist Approach. A decomposition of Total Factor Productivity (TFP) measures (from Standard Full Cumulative Method) revealed that the observed increase in the TFP in ECOWAS agriculture is due to the

efficiency change rather than technological change and as such constitute the main constrained of achieving higher level of TFP during the reference period.

Likewise, Ajao (2012) conducted an empirical analysis of agricultural productivity growth in sub-Saharan Africa for the period 1961-2003, where the study examined changes in agricultural productivity across sub-Saharan African countries in the context of diverse institutional arrangements. The study utilized the Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) method to measure the Malmquist index of total factor productivity to assess productivity changes in the agricultural sector across the region over the sample period. The study also examined the effect of land quality, malaria, education and selected governance indicators such as, control of corruption and government effectiveness on productivity growth have significant impact on the TFP with the exception of government effectiveness and openness.

Similarly, Ajetomobi and Odeniyi (2011) worked on productivity growth in ECOWAS agricultural sector using a nonparametric analysis from a panel data of 13 Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) member nations, spanning from 1971 to 2007. The study also computed Malmquist productivity indexes and its decomposition using Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA). The results showed an average annual TFP decline in the region in the reference period. The TFP change was more attributable to efficiency change than technological change.

In like manner, Yu and Nin-Pratt (2011) conducted a study analyzing the evolution of agricultural total factor productivity (TFP) in Sub-Saharan Africa over the 45-year period from 1961 to 2006. They looked for evidence of recent changes in growth patterns using an improved non-parametric Malmquist index approach. The TFP estimates showed a remarkable recovery in Sub-Saharan African agriculture's performance between 1984 and 2006, after a long preceding period of poor performance and decline. This recovery resulted from improved production efficiency due to changes in output structure and an adjustment in input use. Policy interventions, including fiscal policies, trade policies, and sector-specific policies, appear to have played an important role in improving agricultural performance. Despite this improved performance, Sub-Saharan African economies still face serious challenges to sustain growth, such as the small historical contribution of technical change to TFP growth, the large tax burden from remaining distortions, and the challenge of population growth.

This present study, unlike the previous works, examine the trends and patterns of various production factors influencing the value of agricultural production in ECOWAS, and extend the

years of study to ascertain the effectiveness of certain agricultural policies and programmes like Comprehensive Africa Agriculture Development Programme (CAADP) (2003); ECOWAS Regional Agricultural Policy (ECOWAP); National Agricultural Investment Plans (NAIPs) and the Regional Agricultural Investment Plan (RAIP) (2010) among others on ECOWAS agricultural productivity growth.

3. METHODOLOGY

Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) is a heterogeneous sub-region of Africa that occupies 1.5million km², which represents 17% of the total area of the African continent. The initial fifteen West African countries include: Benin, Burkina Faso, Cape Verde, Côte d'Ivoire, Gambia, Ghana, Guinea, Guinea Bissau, Liberia, Mali, Niger, Nigeria, Senegal, Sierra Leone and Togo. The West African countries cover almost all ecological zones in Africa, ranging from the Sahelian and the Guinea savannah zones in the North to the equatorial rain forest in the South. The natural vegetation ranges from forest to savanna with consistently warm temperature and rainfall ranging from 250mm to over 3000mm per annum (ECOWAS Statistical Bulletin, 2023).

The economy of ECOWAS is typically agrarian and it is characterized by the presence of several small-scale farmers. The agricultural sector constitutes a determining component of the economy of West Africa, due to the size of its contribution to wealth, employment, and food security within the region as well positioning the sub-region in the international markets. The major export commodities are energy products, minerals and agricultural products. The population of ECOWAS grows at an annual rate of 2.29 % and the region had a population of about 424 million in 2023 with Nigeria having the largest population of about 218 million (World data 2023; ECOWAS Statistical Bulletin, 2023).

This study used secondary data. The data is a panel data comprising of output and conventional agricultural inputs (land, labor, fertilizer, and machinery) for the selected ECOWAS countries for the period 1980-2022. The data were accessed from the Food and Agricultural Organization Statistical Database (FAOSTAT), database. The data collected from FAOSTAT include: Value of Agricultural Production (1980-2022); Input data which are: Agricultural land which include total arable land area, permanent cropland and pasture measured in '000 ha, Fertilizer consumption measured in metric tonnes, Agricultural machines which are number of tractors -wheel and crawler- used in agriculture as a measure of the use of modern technological tools, and Rural population measured

in thousands covering the economically active population involved in agriculture.

Data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics such as mean, median, standard deviation, minimum, maximum, skewedness were used to show the trend and pattern of both populations and agricultural growth. The trend analysis was used to identify the trends in the variables employed in the study over a reference period.

Malmquist Productivity Index

The Malmquist productivity index, as proposed by Caves *et al.*, (1982), helps to describe multi-input, multi-output production without involving explicit price data and behavioral assumptions. It is a non-parametric methodology that uses data envelopment analysis (DEA) methods to construct a piece-wise linear production frontier for each country and year in the sample (Ajao, 2012). This methodology has been used extensively for measuring agricultural productivity, as it offers some advantages: a) does not require price information, b) does not assume that all countries are efficient, c) does not assume a behavioral objective function such as cost minimization or revenue/profit maximization, and d) it allows for TFP decomposition into technical change, efficiency change and scale change (Coelli *et al.*, 2005).

Ajao (2012) reported that the output based Malmquist productivity index as a measure of productivity growth was introduced by Cave *et al.*, (1982). They specify the Malmquist productivity index as the geometric mean of these two indices:

$$M_o(x_t, y_t, x_{t+1}, y_{t+1}) = \left[\frac{d_o^t(x_{t+1}, y_{t+1})}{d_o^t(x_t, y_t)} * \frac{d_o^{t+1}(x_{t+1}, y_{t+1})}{d_o^{t+1}(x_t, y_t)} \right] \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Where $d_o^t(x_t, y_t)$ is the output distance for year t , which is defined as the ratio of observed output to the maximum output, y producible with given technology and input vectors, x (Shephard, 1953). The superscript is the value of the output distance evaluated at input-output of year $t+1$ using technology of year t . Equation (1) can be decomposed into the following two components namely efficiency change index which measures the output-oriented shift in technology between two periods and the technical change between period $t+1$ and t . If the technical change is greater (or less) than one, then technological progress (or regress) exists. Here, EFFCH and TECHCH represented efficiency change and technological change respectively.

Symbolically,

$$EFFCH = \frac{d_o^{t+1}(x_{t+1}, y_{t+1})}{d_o^t(x_t, y_t)} \dots\dots\dots(2) \quad \text{and}$$

$$TECHCH = \left[\frac{d_o^t(x_{t+1}, y_{t+1})}{d_o^{t+1}(x_{t+1}, y_{t+1})} \times \frac{d_o^t(x_t, y_t)}{d_o^{t+1}(x_t, y_t)} \right]^{1/2} \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

There exist several methods of estimating the distance functions which makes up the Malmquist TFP index. The most popular and widely adopted in recent time has been the DEA like linear programming (LP) methods suggested by Fare *et al.*, (1994) and its parametric equivalent – stochastic frontier method were adopted in this study.

4. RESULTS AND DISSCUSSION

The Trend Analysis of Agricultural Land Area in ECOWAS

For the trend analysis the trend of the agricultural land area of ECOWAS from 1980 to 2022, the graph revealed a clear and significant upward trend in ECOWAS's agricultural land area within the reference period (1980 to 2022). There was a consistent increase from 1980 to about 2005 showing a steady expansion of agricultural land during this period in ECOWAS. The rate of increase in agricultural land area accelerated slightly from around 2000 to 2005, but a short but noticeable decline was observed around 2010. After the decline observed around 2010, there was a quick recovery in agricultural land area which was sustained by continued rapid growth from 2010 to 2020, representing the most consistent increase in the entire period. This is not in agreement with the work of Faye *et al.*, (2022) that shows that from 2003 to 2019, the total area of agricultural land decreased by –1.4%, while the built-up area expanded by 25.80%. In summary, the ECOWAS agricultural land area was confronted with a lack of management to improve land use efficiency and that there is still room for an expansion of ECOWAS agricultural land area for agricultural purposes, and in this way, increasing food production.

Figure 1: Graph of Agricultural Land Area in the ECOWAS (1980 – 2022)

The Trend Analysis of Fertilizer Consumption in ECOWAS

The graph of the trend of fertilizer consumption in tonnes for ECOWAS from 1980 to 2022 shows that from 1980 to 2000, fertilizer consumption remained low and fairly constant across the ECOWAS region. From 2000 to 2005, there was a sharp increase around 2000, as well as a dramatic sudden rise in fertilizer consumption. From 2005 to 2010, there was a continued rapid growth in fertilizer consumption. From 2010 to 2012, there was a sudden and significant drop in fertilizer consumption. From 2012 to 2022, there was a slow but steady increase in fertilizer consumption until 2022 across the ECOWAS region. This is consistent with the research of Bumb *et al.*, (2012) which shows that the trend of fertilizer consumption in ECOWAS shows low and constant levels from 1980 to 2000, followed by a sharp increase around 2000.

Figure 2: Graph of Fertilizer Consumption in the ECOWAS (1980 – 2022)

The Trend Analysis of Rural Population in ECOWAS

The graph of the rural population trend for ECOWAS from 1980 to 2022 shows a steady, almost linear increase in ECOWAS's rural population. There was a consistent upward trend within the reference period. This is consistent with the work of Faye *et al.*, (2022) where rural population trend for ECOWAS shows a steady, almost linear increase.

Figure 3: Graph of Rural Population in the ECOWAS (1980 – 2022)

The Trend Analysis of Tractorization in ECOWAS

The graph of the trend of tractorization in ECOWAS from 1980 to 2022 shows that from 1980 to 2000, there was a slow but steady increase in the number of tractors. Around 2000 to 2005, there was a sharp increase in the number of tractors. From 2005 to 2010, growth in the number of tractors continued at a rapid pace. There was a significant drop in the number of tractors around 2010. From 2010 to 2022; there was a steady increase again. This is congruent with (Kirui and von Braun, 2018). They found out that the trend of tractorization in ECOWAS shows a complex pattern over the past decades. From 1980 to 2000, there was a slow but steady increase in tractor use. Around 2000 to 2005, a sharp increase in tractorization was observed, followed by rapid growth until 2010. However, a significant drop in tractor numbers occurred around 2010, after which a steady increase resumed until 2022.

Figure 4: Graph of Tractorization in the ECOWAS (1980 – 2022)

The Trend Analysis of Value of Agricultural Production in ECOWAS

The graph of the trend of the value of agricultural production for ECOWAS from 1980 to 2022 shows that from 1980 to 2015, there was a consistent upward trend in agricultural production value. From 2000 to 2015, there was more rapid growth in agricultural output and value. From 2018 to 2020, there was a sharp drop in the agricultural production value. From 2020 to 2022, the trend of agricultural production values has experienced a recovery after the last phase of declining. This is in line with Osabohien and Olurinola, (2021), that found that there was a rapid growth in

agricultural output and value, influence by factors such as rural infrastructure, life expectancy, and political stability.

Figure 5: Graph of Value of Agricultural Production in ECOWAS (1980 – 2022)

Stationarity Test

The summary statistics were utilized to test for unit root in the variables, to avoid spurious regression. The analysis primarily focused on the Levin, Lin & Chu test, while also referencing the Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat test (Table 1). The results also included the ADF - Fisher Chi-square and the PP - Fisher Chi-square tests, which confirmed the stationary status observed with the Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat test across all variables. Specifically, all variables in the model exhibit stationarity at first difference at the 1% level of significance. At levels, only Fertilizer Consumption is stationary across all levels. Rural Population and Agricultural Land Area (ALA) are stationary at 5% and 10% level of significance respectively. The remaining variables demonstrate nonstationarity across all significance levels at the original levels. This suggests that only the variable of Fertilizer Consumption in the model exhibit mean-reversion at the original levels. Upon differencing the variables once, all variables display mean-reversion, with no unit roots at the 1% level of significance, confirming the rejection of the null hypothesis of the presence of unit root.

Table 1: Result of Unit Root Tests

VARIABLES	AT LEVELS	AT FIRST	ORDER OF
	SUMMARY	DIFFERENCE SUMMARY	INTEGRATION
Value of Agricultural	5.8826	-16.2414***	I(1)
Production (VAGP)	5.8031	-14.2966***	
Tractorization	-1.01927	-21.8668***	I(1)
	-0.17802	-18.2747***	
Rural Population	-1.86115**	-15.9674***	I(1)
	2.68262	-14.7514***	
Agricultural Land	-1.38812*	-16.4824***	I(1)
Area (ALA)	1.26984	-16.2410***	
Fertilizer Consumption	-2.17972**	-20.4890***	I(1)
(FC)	-1.28957*	-18.4483***	

Note: Levels of significance are represented thus: 1% (***), 5% (**), 10% (*). First difference values with ** are significant at all levels.

Source: Data Analysis, 2024

Decomposition of TFP of ECOWAS member states agricultural sector into its major components.

Agricultural TFP Growth and Performance of ECOWAS member states: 1980 – 2022

The results of the agricultural total factor productivity growth and performance of ECOWAS member states from using Malmquist DEA indices area shown in Table 2.

From the results, productivity changes for countries in the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) with respect to Efficiency Change (EFFCH) shows that most of the ECOWAS countries have values close to 1, which indicate minimal changes in efficiency, with Togo having the highest efficiency improvement of 1.0128. For the Technical Change (TECHCH), all of the ECOWAS countries in this study show values below 1, which revealed a decline in technological progress, with the range from 0.5950 (Gambia) to 0.7791 (Togo). For the Total Factor Productivity Change (TFPCH), all of the ECOWAS countries in this study values below 1, which indicate an overall productivity decline, ranging from 0.5885 (Gambia) to 0.7926 (Togo).

All the 12 ECOWAS member states studied had negative TFP growth, ranging from -20.74 percent (Togo) to -41.15 percent (Gambia). ECOWAS sub-region as a whole experienced a -33.48 percent decline in productivity. Benin witnessed a negative 34.87 percent growth in agricultural total factor productivity (TFP) within the reference period; Burkina Faso, witnessed a negative 38.53 percent growth in agricultural total factor productivity (TFP) within the reference period; Cote d'Ivoire witnessed a negative 40.21 percent growth in agricultural total factor productivity (TFP) within the reference period; Gambia, witnessed a negative 41.15 percent growth in agricultural total factor productivity (TFP) within the reference period; Ghana, witnessed a negative 37.49 percent growth in agricultural total factor productivity (TFP) within the reference period; Guinea Bissau witnessed a negative 33.7 percent growth in agricultural total factor productivity (TFP) within the reference period; Mali witnessed a negative 33.82 percent growth in agricultural total factor productivity (TFP) within the reference period; Niger witnessed a negative 30.27 percent growth in agricultural total factor productivity (TFP) within the reference period; Nigeria witnessed a negative 30.59 percent growth in agricultural total factor productivity (TFP) within the reference period; Senegal witnessed a negative 28.38 percent growth in agricultural total factor productivity (TFP) within the reference period; Sierra Leone witnessed a negative 23.95 percent growth in agricultural total factor productivity (TFP) within the reference period; Togo witnessed a negative 20.74 percent growth in agricultural total factor productivity (TFP) within

the reference period. ECOWAS as a sub-region witnessed a negative 33.48 percent growth in agricultural total factor productivity (TFP) within the reference period.

From the results above, there is technological regression in ECOWAS agriculture as revealed by the consistently low values of Technological Change (TECHCH), and this is suggesting the need for policies to promote technological adoption and innovation in ECOWAS agriculture. The agricultural sector of ECOWAS is yet experiencing efficiency stagnation as the values of efficiency change (EFFCH) being close to 1 indicate that efficiency levels are not improving significantly, and this points to a need for better resource allocation and management practices in the agricultural sector of the various ECOWAS member states.

There is a severe productivity problem (productivity crisis) in ECOWAS agricultural sector due to the negative total factor productivity (TFPCH) growth across all countries, which could hamper the development of the agricultural sector. Low technical efficiency (TECHCH) and total factor productivity (TFPCH) growth rates across ECOWAS countries revealed there is room for improvement. Negative TFPCH growth rates in most ECOWAS countries suggest there is declining productivity due to variability in efficiency and productivity growth across member countries. The varying degrees of productivity decline indicate that some countries (e.g., Togo, Sierra Leone) are performing better than others (e.g., Gambia, Côte D'Ivoire), revealing potential for regional learning and cooperation, investment in technology and innovation, technology transfer and adoption, education and skill development, research and development (R&D), infrastructure development, institutional reforms, access to finance, and monitoring and evaluation. This agrees with Abekah-Koomson *et al.*, (2021) who reported an average annual decline in Total Factor Productivity (TFP) in the agricultural sector from 1971 to 2007, attributing this more to efficiency change than technological change. But disagree with Nkamleu (2004) who reported positive TFP evolution in 16 African countries from 1970-2001, driven by improved technical efficiency rather than technological progress. noted overall good TFP performance in ECOWAS countries, despite significant drops in the late 1990s and 2000s, possibly due to global financial crises. They also found that Technical Efficiency in the region was below optimal production levels.

The reasons for the above scenario are not far-fetched and from previous and recent empirical works, it may be due to the following: ECOWAS member States are heavily reliant on agricultural exports, making them vulnerable to fluctuations in global commodity prices, Seka,

(2009); The region's trade is dominated by a few countries, including Nigeria, Ghana, Côte d'Ivoire, and Senegal, with a limited range of agricultural commodities being exported (ECOWAS Statistical Bulletin, 2021); The lack of diversification makes the region susceptible to external shocks, including changes in global market prices; The ECOWAS region faces several challenges, including a high level of poverty, low life expectancy, and limited access to education and healthcare (World Bank, 2021); The region's agricultural sector is also underdeveloped, with low productivity and limited investment in modern technology and research, resulting in a significant reliance on food imports, which has been costly and unpredictable; The present level of resources (technical, technological, financial, etc.) in the sub-region have not allow ECOWAS member states to experience true economic liberalization (UNECA, 2012; Ogbonna *et al.*, 2013); Conflict and political instability have also hindered the region's development, with several countries experiencing civil wars and coups Atuobi, (2007); Corruption is also a significant problem, with many countries in the region ranking highly on corruption indices leading to a lack of trust in governments and institutions, making it difficult to implement effective policies and programs (Transparency International, 2006); The ECOWAS region has experienced several challenges in its efforts to promote economic integration and cooperation, including limited intra-regional trade and a reliance on external partners (Gbadebo, 2004). So, to tackle the above challenges which impact on the agricultural TFP growth in ECOWAS sub-region, the sub-region needs to focus on diversifying its exports, investing in modern technology and research, and promoting regional integration and cooperation (IFPRI, 2010; World Bank, 2021).

Table 2: Summary of ECOWAS Member States’ Results of TFP Decomposition from Traditional Malmquist DEA Method Showing TFP Growth and Performance

COUNTRY	EFFCH	TECHCH	TFPCH	TFPCH GROWTH	TFPCH GROWTH (%)
Benin	1.0025	0.6460	0.6513	- 0.3487	- 34.87
Burkina Faso	1.0029	0.6114	0.6147	- 0.3853	- 38.53
Cote D’Ivoire	1.0030	0.5968	0.5979	- 0.4021	- 40.21
Gambia	0.9957	0.5950	0.5885	- 0.4115	- 41.15
Ghana	0.9974	0.6281	0.6251	- 0.3749	- 37.49
Guinea Bissau	0.9959	0.6670	0.6630	- 0.337	- 33.7
Mali	0.9975	0.6682	0.6618	-0.3382	- 33.82
Niger	0.9935	0.7044	0.6973	- 0.3027	- 30.27
Nigeria	0.9986	0.7001	0.6941	- 0.3059	- 30.59
Senegal	1.0002	0.7193	0.7162	- 0.2838	- 28.38
Sierra Leone	1.0048	0.7594	0.7605	- 0.2395	- 23.95
Togo	1.0128	0.7791	0.7926	- 0.2074	- 20.74
ECOWAS	0.9994	0.6690	0.6652	- 0.3348	- 33.48

Source: Data Analysis, 2024

Figure 6: Graph of the Trend of the Total Factor Productivity in ECOWAS 1980 – 2022)

Source: Data Analysis, 2024

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The ECOWAS region has experienced a decline in agricultural productivity within the reference period (1980 - 2022), as all the 12 member states studied experienced negative Total Factor Productivity (TFP) growth. Hence, the sub region's agricultural TFP growth rate has declined by 33.48% due to technological regression and efficiency stagnation. Based on the need to enhance agricultural productivity in a bid to ensure food security, and promote sustainable economic growth in the ECOWAS sub-region, this study therefore recommends increased investment in farm mechanization (tractorization) as well as increased investment in agricultural production inputs, technologies and practices to boost agricultural production and drive ECOWAS agricultural productivity growth.

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